

USE OF COMPOUNDS WITH ALIPHATIC CARBAMATE GROUP IN PHARMACEUTICS

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Annotation: In this article, the reaction rate and isomer composition of carbamate and bis-carbamate derivatives were studied by determining the reactivity of N-H alkylated compounds with alkyl halides. The effect of factors such as the radical nature, branching and length of the molecule, the solvent and the "hardness" or "softness" of the methylating agent was investigated.

Keywords: carbamate, bis-carbamate, isocyanate, carbon-nitrogen bond, N,N'-disodium derivative, methyl iodide, benzene.

Introduction.

In recent years, in the chemistry of synthetic organic compounds, as well as in various branches of industry, the direction of synthesis of organic substances by fractional synthesis has been developing, among which special attention has been paid to carbamate and bis-carbamate derivatives derived from isocyanates, as well as to hydroxyl-containing radicals, and in this respect certain results have been achieved in the development of materials in which derivatives of carbamates and bis-carbamates are used as various technical, biological and pharmacological active substances.

Compounds with an aliphatic carbamate group ($-\text{NH}_2\text{COO}-$) are widely used in the pharmaceutical industry due to their unique pharmacological properties. These compounds have a variety of mechanisms of action and can be used as active pharmaceutical ingredients in various classes of drugs such as analgesics, antidepressants, anticonvulsants and others.

Use of compounds with an aliphatic carbamate group in the pharmaceutical industry

Some aliphatic carbamates, such as pyrimidone, are used as anticonvulsants in the treatment of epilepsy. These substances have the ability to stabilise neuronal membranes, preventing excessive excitation of neurons.

Pyrimidone is a drug that affects neurotransmission in the brain, helping to prevent seizures and epileptic fits.

Some carbamate compounds are used to make painkillers. These substances can act on the central nervous system to alter the perception of pain. An example

trihydrotetrafluoropropylcarbamate, at a concentration of 1 mg/kg haemoglobin, has a selective immunotropic activity, increasing the level of antibodies in peripheral blood in cases of secondary immunodeficiency caused by cyclophosphamide.

The use of pulse technology for the emulsion extraction of isoprenoids from plant raw materials and the extraction of substances with regulatory properties has been demonstrated. Polyene alcohols, a substance that performs the function of transporting hydrophilic particles across the cell membrane, have been isolated. These substances serve as the basis for the creation of substances with a broad spectrum of activity against rapidly evolving viruses. Triterpenic acids have been isolated from thorny fir. Salts of these acids with Na, K, Cu were obtained and preparations were made on their basis. Systematic testing of biopreparations, seed processing and their growth-regulating activity when applied to plants during the growing season has been found. Taking into account the seriousness of the ecological situation and the increase in oncological diseases, a technology for obtaining bioregulators was developed.

Conclusion

Compounds with an aliphatic carbamate group play an important role in the pharmaceutical industry, providing effective treatments for a variety of diseases, including epilepsy, depression, anxiety disorders and some types of cancer. They are widely used in both human and veterinary medicine, but their toxicity and side effects are of concern.

